

ASSORTMENT ANALYSIS OF HORMONAL DRUGS REGISTERED IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Relevance: hormones are important for a person to lead an active life. Hormones regulate all the processes that go in the body, support its stability, respond to external and internal changes, while controlling reproductive health and growth. If the hormonal balance fails, it leads to negative consequences such as stress, fatigue, changes in weight, metabolic disorders. Relevance: hormones are important for a person to lead an active life. Hormones regulate all the processes that go in.

Purpose of the study: analysis of hormonal drugs based on the State Register of medicines and medical products registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods: on the basis of the State Register of medicines and medical products registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan, an assortment analysis of hormonal drugs was carried out using qualimetric methods.

Results: during the research, an analysis was carried out on the total amount, width, depth and renewal indicator of hormonal drugs allowed for use in the CIS countries, in the Republic and abroad, and hormonal drugs registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan were studied between 2020 and 2024. According to this, in 2020, it was found that hormonal drugs produced by domestic manufacturers accounted for 20%, the CIS countries accounted for 27.37%, and hormonal drugs produced by foreign manufacturers accounted for 52.63%. According to this, in 2020, it was found that hormonal drugs produced by domestic manufacturers accounted for 20%, the CIS countries accounted for 27.37%, and hormonal drugs produced by foreign manufacturers accounted for 52.63%. And in 2024, hormonal drugs produced by domestic manufacturers accounted for 28.23%, the CIS countries accounted for 16.13%, and hormonal drugs produced by foreign manufacturers accounted for 55.65%. During the analysis, an analysis was carried out on the depth indicator of hormonal drugs registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024. In this, the CIS countries accounted for 10%, in the foreign countries this figure was 4.35%. At the next stage of the analysis, an analysis was carried out on the hormonal drug renewal index. During the analysis, an analysis was carried out on the depth indicator of hormonal drugs registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024.

Conclusions: as of 2024, the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan has been found to contain hormonal drugs with 124 different trade names. The bulk of hormonal drugs in the pharmaceutical market-55.65% - are drugs imported from foreign countries or manufactured there.